

A Hybrid Method and C Language Implementation for Higher Order Equations Based on Newton-Raphson Method and Bisection Method

Chenxi Li

College of Electronic Engineering/College of Artificial Intelligence, South China

Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, PR China

E-MAIL:814792356@qq.com

Abstract: Considering the difficulty in solving higher order equations, this paper proposes a hybrid numerical computation method based on the Newton-Raphson method and the bisection method. Firstly, the paper detailedly studies the fundamental principle of the hybrid method by combining the global convergence of the bisection method and the local fast convergence of the Newton-Raphson method. Then, the hybrid method is implemented in C language. Finally, numerical experiments verify the effectiveness of the hybrid method.

Keywords: Higher order equations; Bisection method; Newton-Raphson method; Hybrid method; C language

I. Introduction

The problem of solving higher order equations in the form of $a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0 = 0$ is a research hotspot in the field of mathematics, and has a broad application in the fields of science and engineering. However, according to Abelian's theorem [1], there is no general way to find an algebraic solution to a polynomial equation of more than five degrees. Therefore, it is particularly important to find efficient and accurate numerical computation methods. Traditional numerical methods, such as the Newton-Raphson method [2-5] and bisection methods [6,7], have their own shortcomings. The bisection method converges slowly, and the Newton-Raphson method is sensitive to the initial value. Hence, combining with the bisection method and Newton-Raphson method, this paper proposes a hybrid numerical computation method, which aims to not only ensure convergence but also improve the convergence speed.

The outline of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives a brief account of bisection method and the Newton-Raphson method. Section 3 detailedly discusses the fundamental principles of the proposed hybrid method and its implementation in C language [8,9]. In section 4, an example of a simulation is given. A conclusion is drawn in Section 5.

II. Preliminaries

This section briefly reviews the principles of the bisection method and Newton-Raphson iterative methods to facilitate the proposal of the subsequent hybrid methods.

2.1 Bisection method

The bisection method is essentially an interval iterative method, which continuously dividing the root interval into two parts during the iterative process, so that the two endpoints of the interval are gradually approached to the zero point, and then the approximate value of the root is obtained.

According to the mediator theorem of continuous functions, let the function $f(x)$ be continuous over the interval $[a, b]$ and satisfy the condition $f(a) \cdot f(b) < 0$, in this way $f(x) = 0$ has at least one root in the interval $[a, b]$. First, we calculate the midpoint $x_0 (x_0 = 0.5(a + b))$ of interval $[a, b]$, and then analyze the following three possible scenarios:

- (1) If $f(x_0) \cdot f(a) < 0$, there is a zero point within the interval $[a, x_0]$;
- (2) if $f(x_0) \cdot f(a) > 0$, there is a zero point within the interval $[x_0, b]$;
- (3) if $f(x_0) = 0$, then x_0 is the zero point within the interval $[a, b]$.

If one of the first two cases occurs, it means that an interval with a partition that is halved than the length of the original interval is found, and the rootless interval is discarded. In the next calculation, the root interval will be divided into two, and a smaller interval will be found, and so on, the root interval will be reduced to a sufficiently small size, and finally an approximation that meets the accuracy requirements will be obtained.

2.2 Newton-Raphson method

Assuming the given equation $f(x) = 0$ has an approximate solution, the derivative of the function $f(x)$ is $f'(x)$. Here we will expand Taylor at the point x_k and take the first two terms and then we can obtain:

$$f(x) \approx f(x_k) + f'(x_k)(x - x_k)$$

Due to $f(x) = 0$, then:

$$f(x_k) + f'(x_k)(x - x_k) = 0$$

Solve this linear equation:

$$x = x_k - \frac{f(x_k)}{f'(x_k)}$$

Obtain the iterative formula:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - \frac{f(x_k)}{f'(x_k)} \quad (k = 0, 1, \dots) \quad (1)$$

This formula (1) is called the Newton-Raphson iterative formula. Only when the initial value x_0 is close enough to the zero point will it converge to the zero point very quickly.

III. the Hybrid Method and C Language Implementation

3.1 The hybrid method

Combining the global convergence of the bisection method and the local fast convergence of the Newton-Raphson method, a hybrid method for numerical computation is proposed in this section, which improves the efficiency and reliability of solving higher order equations. Firstly, according to the solution interval given by the high order equation in question, the global convergence of the bisection method is used to narrow the interval. Then, in the preliminarily narrowed interval, the Newton-Raphson method is used to iteratively solve the solution to meet the accuracy requirements.

3.2 Implementation in C language

This section discusses in detail how to implement the proposed hybrid method using the C language. The specific steps are as follows:

1) Declare the required functions: 'func()' and derivation() to facilitate the subsequent definition of the higher order equation in the 'func()' function, and define the derivative of the equation in the 'derivative()' function.

The specific C language procedure is as follows.

```
// Function declaration
double func(double x);
double derivative(double x);
```

2) Take the midpoint in the initial interval and calculate the function value of that point. The A and B are the left and right boundary values of the interval, respectively. If the value of the function is the same as the sign of B, the interval is narrowed to the left half; Otherwise, zoom out to the right half. Repeat this step until the interval is small enough.

The specific C language procedure is as follows.

```
//using bisection method to narrow the interval
double bisection(double A, double B, double tolerance)
{
    double mid;
    while (fabs(B - A) > tolerance)
    {
        mid = (A + B) / 2;
        if (func(A) * func(mid) < 0) B = mid;
        else A = mid;
    }
    return (A + B) / 2;
}
```

3) The median value is taken within the narrowed interval as the initial value of the Newton-Raphson iteration. Using Newton-Raphson iterative formula (1), iterative calculations are performed until the accuracy requirements are met.

The specific C language procedure is as follows.

```
// approximating the root using Newton-Raphson method
double newton(double x0, double tolerance)
{
    double x = x0;
    while (fabs(func(x)) > tolerance)
```

```
{  
    x = x - func(x) / derivative(x);  
}  
return x;  
}
```

4) Set the accuracy 'tolerance', which indicates the accuracy requirement. Set the initial interval of the root: the A and B are the left and right boundary values of the interval, respectively.

The specific C language procedure is as follows.

```
// Set initial interval and calculation accuracy  
int main()  
{  
    double A, B, root, tolerance = 1e-6;  
    return 0;  
}
```

IV. Application Examples

In this section, we take the higher order equation $x^5 - 3x^4 + 2x^3 - x + 1 = 0$ as an example to solve its roots on $[-2, 0]$ quickly and efficiently.

```
// Construct the higher order equation  
double func(double x) {  
    return pow(x, 5) - 3 * pow(x, 4) + 2 * pow(x, 3) - x + 1;  
}  
  
// functional derivative  
double derivative(double x) {  
    return 5 * pow(x, 4) - 12 * pow(x, 3) + 6 * pow(x, 2) - 1;  
}  
  
// Set the initial interval of the root and accuracy  
  
int main() {  
    double a, b, root, tolerance = 1e-6;  
    a = -2; b = 0;  
  
    // Use the bisection method to narrow down the interval  
    root = bisection(a, b, tolerance);  
}
```

```
// Newton-Raphson method is used to solve iteratively within this interval
```

```
root = newton(root, tolerance);
```

```
printf("The root of the equation is:%lf\n", root);
```

```
return 0;
```

```
}
```

The running result is: -1.137877. Experimental results show that this hybrid method improves the stability and convergence speed of numerical computation.

V. Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a hybrid method for numerical computation to solve higher order equations. The method effectively improves the stability and convergence speed of numerical computation. Implemented through C language, the method is concise and not only easy to understand but to extend. The hybrid method is convenient for solving the roots of higher order equations, and has a wide range of application prospects in the fields of engineering and scientific computing.

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